

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LITERARY RELATIONS.

Dadebayeva Malika Miratbayevna

Student at Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15779461>

Abstract. This article studies the historical development of Uzbek and Karakalpak literary relations. The theoretical foundations of literary relations between the literatures of blood-related peoples are analyzed.

Keywords: Uzbek literature, Karakalpak literature, folklore, lyrics, socialization, artistry, nationality, literary influence.

The process of formation of each nation includes long historical stages. In this process, the interaction, cultural exchange and political unification of different peoples, clans and tribes play an important role. The historical roots and ethnogenetic foundations of the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples should also be considered on the basis of the inextricable ties between these Turkic peoples.

In this regard, the research of well-known scientists, including the Kazakh scientist Shokan Valikhonov and the Russian scientist V. Sheglov, serves as an important source. The fact that Shokan Valikhonov's mother was a Karakalpak and that he called the Karakalpaks "Mang'itlar" in his research is an important evidence for the historical naming of this people. Sheglov, as an accomplished specialist who has studied the archaeological and ethnographic aspects of the history of the Karakalpaks, substantiates this idea.

Analysis of historical sources shows that the Mangit and Kungirat clans played a key role in the ethnogenesis of the Karakalpaks. Although political conflicts between these two peoples in the 12th-13th centuries indicate the complex dynamics of historical periods, the strong dominance of the Mangits in the 14th-16th centuries and the Kungirats in the 17th-18th centuries is noted. The centers of these dominance were the Edil-Jayyk (Volga-Ural) oasis for the Mangits, and Khorezm for the Kungirats. These facts confirm that the synthesis of several Turkic components played an important role in the formation of the Karakalpak people.

From this point of view, the Karakalpak and Uzbek peoples are closely connected not only by geographical proximity, but also by common historical and ethnic roots.

Most of the Karakalpak clans are also found among the Uzbeks. This indicates that the two peoples have lived together for a long time. Therefore, there is a close relationship between their language, customs, lifestyle and rituals. In particular, the Karakalpak song "haujar" and the Uzbek ritual song

"yor-yor" are almost identical in content and musical expression. This similarity is manifested not only in appearance, but also in the internal spiritual content, in the system of values.

The territories of residence - Khorezm, Turkestan, the Volga and Ural rivers - have also been the common homeland of the two peoples. The cultural heritage formed in these territories is an integral part of the history of the Turkic peoples.

The connections between Uzbek and Karakalpak oral literature are close not only in form, but also in semantic content. Epics such as "Alpomish", "Edigey", "Maspasha", "Shariyar", "Qoblan" are accepted by both peoples as their own literary property. It is difficult to be precise about their origin, because these works are the product of folk memory and cultural exchange, and they embody pan-Turkic images.

Examples of short genres of oral literature such as proverbs, sayings and proverbs also express the common spirit between these peoples. For example, in the Uzbek language:

O'zga elning sultoni bo'lguncha, o'z elingning cho'poni bo'l or
Qimirlagan qir oshar, qolgan ishga qor yog'ar –

Proverbs such as these also exist in the Karakalpak language in exactly the same form:

Ózge eldiń sultanı bolǵansha, óz elińniń shopanı bol.
Qıymılǵan qır asar, qalǵan iske qar jawar.

This means that examples of oral creativity have survived, having passed from one people to another, without losing themselves. Such cultural exchanges mean that folklore transcends national borders and should be perceived as a "national memory".

In today's globalization environment, it is important to reassess and develop cultural and literary ties between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples at a new level. The statement of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "I am a child not only of the Uzbek people, but also of the Karakalpak people" is a political expression of the historical, cultural and spiritual unity between the two peoples.

Such thoughts serve as an extremely important signal for modern historical politics and the principles of interethnic relations. The common literary heritage of the Turkic peoples is a symbol of their spiritual and cultural unity, not their political one. The ideas of pan-Turkic unity, humanism and nationalism occupy a central place in the work of such scholars as Alisher Navoi, Makhtumkuli, Abay, Berdak.

The ethnic, linguistic, traditional and literary ties between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples confirm that these two peoples were formed on the basis of an indissoluble historical and cultural unity. This unity is not only the wealth of the past, but also a strong foundation for future development. Therefore, the scientific study of cultural ties, comparison, translation, study and promotion of folklore and literature do not lose their relevance today.

The rich history of cultural, ethnic and linguistic ties between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples is based on the common roots of the Turkic peoples that developed in the territories of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. The process of the origin of these peoples includes the interaction, mergers and migrations of various ethnic groups, tribes and cultures. It is very important to take into account the interconnections between the Turkic peoples in understanding their historical, cultural and linguistic ties.

Scientific studies on the origin of the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples offer different views. The formation of the Uzbek people is considered to have occurred between the 13th and 15th centuries, including during the Golden Horde and the Shaybanids. Although the Karakalpak people had a solid ethnogenetic foundation in the 14th century, the Mangit and Kungirat tribes played an important role in their ethnogenesis. The Turkic heritage and cultures of the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples are very closely related. The similarities between these peoples are also reflected in their historical, linguistic and cultural traditions.

The closeness of literary and oral creativity between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples confirms their common cultural past. The oral creative works of these peoples, such as epics such as "Alpomish", "Edigey", "Maspatsha", together constitute a pan-Turkic heritage. These works are of equal importance for the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples, have been preserved in the memory of the people and represent the exchange of different cultures. Such similarities are reflected not only in formal aspects, but also in their semantic content.

The territories of residence of the Uzbeks and Karakalpaks are very close to each other - Khorezm, Turkestan, the Volga and Urals - these territories have enhanced cultural exchange and interaction between the peoples. As a result, similarities have arisen between their customs, rituals and folk musical art. In particular, the folk songs of the Karakalpaks and Uzbeks, for example, ceremonial songs such as "haujar" and "yor-yor", are very similar in music and content, which confirms the spiritual and cultural closeness of these peoples to each other. In conclusion, it can be noted that the cultural and literary ties

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

between the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples continue to move to a new stage. The statement of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "I am a child not only of the Uzbek people, but also of the Karakalpak people" further strengthens the historical and cultural unity of the two peoples. The scientific study and promotion of the ties between the literary heritage and traditions of these peoples is still an urgent task today. Thanks to this, the ideas of the unity of the Turkic peoples, humanism and patriotism once again confirm their importance.

References:

1. Kurambaev K. Adabiy ta'sirdan ijodiy o'ziga xoslikka. – N.: «Qoraqalpog'iston» 2007.
2. Kurambaev K. Tarjima va tarjimon mas'uliyati. –T.: «Cho'lpon» 2007.
3. Kurambaev K. Adabiy jarayon, Ijod mas'uliyati. Adabiy aloqalar. –T.: 2009.
4. Kurambayeva G. O'zbek va qoraqalpoq adabiy aloqalari (adabiy aloqa, o'zaro ta'sir va badiiy tarjima) fil. fan. dok. diss. Nukus 2023

